

The sFlt-1/Plgf Ratio as a Diagnostic Biomarker for Preeclampsia: A Systematic Review

I Kadek Ade Juniantara¹, Nyoman Gede Dikawijaya Satriawan², Anak Agung Istri Agung Aprilla Berlianti³, I Putu Willy Ganang Arta Putra⁴

¹Bali Royal Mother and Child Hospital (BROS Ina), Denpasar, Bali

³Departement of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Udayana University/Prof Ngoerah Hospital, Denpasar, Bali

^{1,2,3,4}Faculty of Medicine, Udayana University, Denpasar, Bali

ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Published Online: 12 June 2026</p>	<p>Background: Preeclampsia (PE) is a medical condition associated with placental and maternal endothelial dysfunction that can lead to complications and long-term health problems affecting both the mother and the child. Previous studies have shown that the ratio of soluble fms-like tyrosine kinase-1 (sFlt-1) to placental growth factor (PlGF) has potential in the diagnosis of PE.</p> <p>Objective: This systematic review aims to determine the role of the sFlt-1/PlGF ratio as a diagnostic biomarker in preeclampsia.</p> <p>Methods: This systematic review was conducted based on the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines. A comprehensive literature search was performed using three electronic databases, namely PubMed, ScienceDirect, and Cochrane, up to February 2026. The inclusion criteria included studies analyzing the sFlt-1/PlGF ratio in pregnant women with singleton pregnancies. This review analyzed the cut-off values, area under the curve (AUC), sensitivity, and specificity.</p> <p>Results: Four studies were included in this review, which consist of two case-control studies and two prospective cohort studies. The reported cut-off values for the sFlt-1/PlGF ratio varied across studies, including <33, <38, and ≥85. All studies demonstrated good diagnostic performance with AUC values ranging from 0.80 to 0.94. The reported sensitivity and specificity were also relatively high in detecting the occurrence of preeclampsia in pregnant women.</p> <p>Conclusion: The sFlt-1/PlGF ratio is a potential biomarker that can improve the diagnostic accuracy of PE in pregnant women. The use of the sFlt-1/PlGF ratio may support patient condition identification and facilitate earlier clinical decision-making in the management of pregnancies at risk of PE.</p>
<p>Corresponding Author: I Kadek Ade Juniantara</p>	
<p>KEYWORDS: sFlt1/PlGF, diagnostic, preeclampsia, ratio</p>	

I. INTRODUCTION

Preeclampsia is a serious medical condition during pregnancy that affects between 5% and 8% of all pregnancies. Globally, the prevalence of preeclampsia varies, and the condition is generally more common in developing countries. Furthermore, preeclampsia accounts for approximately 14% of all maternal mortalities.¹ Additionally, the global mortality figures for preeclampsia amount to around 500.000 fetal/neonatal deaths and 70.000 maternal deaths annually.² Clinically, preeclampsia is a condition characterized by the onset of hypertension after 20 weeks of gestation. Moreover, preeclampsia is a condition

that also involves dysfunction in other organ systems in the mother. Renal dysfunction is the most frequently observed manifestation, typically characterized by the presence of proteinuria. Other organ involvement may include the liver, respiratory system, cardiovascular system, central nervous system, and hematological disorders.¹

Previous studies have indicated that the exact cause of preeclampsia remains unclear. However, this condition is widely believed to result from placental hypoperfusion caused by abnormal remodeling of the maternal spiral arteries.³ The identification of circulating angiogenic factors in the pathogenesis of preeclampsia represents a significant

advancement in both diagnostic and prognostic aspects. Furthermore, previous studies have indicated that circulating angiogenic factors, specifically, *soluble fms-like tyrosine kinase 1* (sFlt-1) and the pro-angiogenic factor of Placental Growth Factor (PlGF), are molecules that can be measured in plasma and serum using automated platforms and reported as a ratio. Both molecules are primarily produced by the placenta and serve as non-invasive biomarkers of placental health.² The sFlt-1 molecule, which acts as an antagonist to PlGF and VEGF, exhibits increased expression in the preeclampsia placenta, leading to elevated systemic sFlt-1 levels and reduced circulating PlGF levels. Due to this antagonistic effect, sFlt-1 triggers vasoconstriction and endothelial dysfunction, which may ultimately lead to fetal growth restriction and preeclampsia.^{3,4} Notably, the sFlt-1/PlGF ratio increases in pregnant women 4–5 weeks prior to the clinical onset of the disease. Other studies have shown that measuring the ratio of these two molecules has higher predictive value compared to the use of either biomarker in isolation.^{3,5}

Proteinuria and elevated blood pressure are the primary diagnostic criteria for preeclampsia; however, its clinical manifestations vary significantly. Therefore, a reliable diagnostic biomarker is required to assess the likelihood of preeclampsia, particularly to exclude the diagnosis in women with suspected preeclampsia.³

Given this context, the present systematic review was conducted to analyze the role of the sFlt-1/PlGF ratio as a diagnostic biomarker in the incidence of preeclampsia.

II. METHOD

This systematic review was conducted in accordance with the Priority Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines, as illustrated in Figure 1.

A. Literature Search Strategy and Inclusion Criteria

A comprehensive literature search was performed across three databases: PubMed, ScienceDirect, and Cochrane. Studies were selected based on specific inclusion criteria using the search terms “sFlt-1/PlGF,” “preeclampsia,” and “diagnosis.” The search was limited to articles published in English. Other article types, such as literature reviews and previous systematic reviews, were utilized as supplemental data and for comparative analysis within the discussion section.

B. Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

The inclusion criteria for this systematic review were as follows: 1) Articles published in English, and 2) Studies analyzing the diagnostic performance of the sFlt-1/PlGF ratio in relation to the incidence of preeclampsia. The exclusion criteria for this study included: 1) Certain study types, such as literature reviews, protocols only, case reports, conference proceedings, non-full-text articles, and

qualitative studies, and 2) studies with data that did not align with the specified outcomes of this review.

C. Quality Assessment of Studies

The methodological quality of the included studies was assessed using the Quality Assessment of Diagnostic Accuracy Studies-2 (QUADAS-2) tool. This method is specifically designed to evaluate studies concerning the accuracy of diagnostic tests. The QUADAS-2 tool consists of four key domains: patient selection, index test, reference standard, and flow and timing.

D. Data Extraction and Analysis

Data were extracted from each included study using a pilot-tested data extraction form. The information gathered from each study included the country of origin, sample size, study design, population characteristics, and research findings. The collected data were then interpreted both qualitatively and quantitatively. By analyzing the findings and identifying trends across the included studies, a conclusion was drawn regarding the role of the sFlt-1/PlGF ratio as a diagnostic biomarker for preeclampsia.

Figure 1. PRISMA Flow Diagram of the Literature Search Process

III. RESULT

Based on the analysis conducted, four studies were identified that evaluate the diagnostic accuracy of the sFlt-1/PlGF ratio in preeclampsia. These studies were assessed using several indicators, including the area under the curve (AUC), sensitivity, specificity, cut-off values, negative predictive value (NPV), and positive predictive value (PPV). Regarding demographic characteristics, the included studies covered diverse populations, including China, Japan, several European countries, and multinational cohorts. This systematic review includes four studies, consisting of two case-control designs and two prospective designs. The characteristics of the studies meeting the inclusion criteria are presented in Table 1. Furthermore, the risk of bias assessment for these studies is illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Methodological Quality Assessment Using QUADAS-2

The quality assessment showed that all four studies had some risk of bias. The studies by Zeisler (2016) and Ohkuchi (2021) had a low risk of bias, while those by Ding

(2018) and Stepan (2016) showed a moderate risk. Details of this assessment are shown in Figure 2

Table 1. Study Characteristic

Author (Year)	Country	Study Design	Population (n)	Gestational Age (week)	Sample (n)	Cut-off	AUC (95% CI)	Sensitivity (%)	Specificity (%)	NPV (%)	PPV (%)
Ding (2018) ⁵	China	Case-control	486 (136 pre-eclampsia, 350 controls)	≥20	486	>38,83	0,802 (0,753–0,851)	57,4	95,1	NR	NR
Ohkuchi (2021) ⁴	Japan	Prospective	180	18-36	180	≤38 (1-week rule-out)	0,952 (0,914-0,982)	100	83,1	100	NR
						>38 (4-weeks rule-in)	0,906 (0,845-0,955)	75,0	84,8	NR	32,4
Stepan (2016) ⁶	Multicenter (European regions)	Case-control	569 (178 cases, 391 controls)	<34 and ≥34	569	33 (rule-out)/ 85 (rule-in) for early-onset (<34 weeks)	0,982 (0,965-0,999)	94,0	99,4	NR	NR
						33 (rule-out)/ 110 (rule-in) for late-onset (≥34 weeks)	0,888 (0,846-0,931)	89,5	95,4	NR	NR
Zeisler (2016) ³	Multicenter	Prospective	1050 (550 derivations, 550 validations)	24-36	550	≤38 (1-week rule-out)	0,861 (0,798-0,924)	80,0	78,3	99,3	NR
						>38 (4-weeks rule-in)	0,823 (0,773-0,873)	66,2	83,1	NR	36,7

Based on the results presented in Table 1, the four included studies demonstrate that the sFlt-1/PlGF ratio possesses high diagnostic performance for detecting preeclampsia, with AUC values ranging from 0.802 to 0.982. This systematic review also indicates that the diagnostic capacity of this ratio varies and is significantly dependent on gestational age. According to the study by Stepan (2016), the AUC value reached 0.982 for early-onset preeclampsia (<34 weeks). In this phase, sensitivity reached 94.0% with a specificity of 99.4% using a rule-in cutoff of ≥ 85 . Conversely, for late-onset preeclampsia (>34 weeks), the diagnostic accuracy decreased slightly (AUC 0.888). While the specificity remained relatively stable at 95.4%, the cutoff value increased to >110.

The results of this study demonstrate that using a cutoff of 38 yields a very high NPV, ranging from 99.3% to 100%, for ruling out preeclampsia within one week. Conversely, the PPV for predicting the condition within four weeks was moderate, ranging from 32.4% to 36.7%. Additionally, the findings highlight variations across ethnic populations. Specifically, the study by Ding (2018) reported a lower cutoff value (>24.50) in the Han Chinese population compared to non-Han ethnicities (Uygur, Kazakh, Hui) and global populations.

IV. DISCUSSION

The results of this systematic review demonstrate that the sFlt-1/PlGF ratio exhibits reliable diagnostic performance in the identification of preeclampsia.

In this review, all included studies reported AUC values >0.8. These findings align with previous research indicating AUC values for the sFlt-1/PlGF ratio of 0.834 and 0.90.^{7,8} Furthermore, studies comparing the ratio to standalone biomarkers—specifically sFlt-1 and PlGF—showed lower AUC values of 0.749 and 0.795, respectively. This indicates that the sFlt-1/PlGF ratio is a superior diagnostic biomarker compared to single-marker assessments.⁷ Most studies in this review also demonstrated high sensitivity and specificity (both >80%), consistent with prior data showing values of 84.2% and 85%.⁸ Notably, the ratio showed significant strength in short-term rule-out strategies, where a cutoff of ≤ 38 consistently yielded a very high NPV (99.3% to 100%) for excluding preeclampsia within one week. Conversely, the four-week PPV remained moderate (32.4% to 40.7%). Variability in cutoff values may also be influenced by differences in the automated platforms used for measurement.

The sFlt-1/PlGF ratio plays a critical role in the pathophysiology of both early-onset and late-onset preeclampsia. The syncytiotrophoblast surface, which is in direct contact with maternal blood, is highly susceptible to damage and serves as the primary source of preeclampsia biomarkers, including sFlt-1. Elevated sFlt-1 levels lead to a decrease in free PlGF due to direct binding between the two molecules. This mechanism is primarily observed in early-

onset preeclampsia. In contrast, the angiogenic/anti-angiogenic imbalance in late-onset preeclampsia is more heavily influenced by lifestyle factors and maternal metabolic disorders that trigger syncytiotrophoblast stress. Physiologically, PlGF supports the development and maturation of the placental vascular system; however, in preeclampsia, PlGF levels decline as a consequence of sFlt-1 sequestration. While sFlt-1 naturally rises and PlGF falls during the final two months of normotensive pregnancies, these changes occur earlier and more significantly in women who subsequently develop preeclampsia.

In conclusion, the results of this study, which encompass diverse ethnic populations, demonstrate promising diagnostic accuracy, suggesting that the sFlt-1/PlGF ratio has significant potential as a diagnostic biomarker for preeclampsia. Nonetheless, certain limitations must be acknowledged, specifically the inclusion of case-control studies, which may introduce a potential risk of bias regarding diagnostic accuracy. Additionally, adjustments for the specific automated platforms used across different studies remain a necessary consideration.

V. CONCLUSIONS & SUGESSTION

This systematic review shows that the sFlt-1/PlGF ratio is a strong biomarker for diagnosing and predicting preeclampsia worldwide. Its effectiveness is proven across multiple measures, including AUC, sensitivity, specificity, PPV, and NPV. In the future, using this ratio can help doctors identify patient conditions earlier and make better clinical decisions when managing high-risk pregnancies.

REFERENCES

1. Rahmatullah MR, Dewi R, Sari P, Romulya AI, Kedokteran F, Lampung U, et al. Epidemiologi dan Diagnosis Preeklamsia. *Medula*. 2024;14(2):276–80.
2. Verlohren S, Brennecke SP, Galindo A, Karumanchi SA, Mirkovic LB, Schlembach D, et al. Clinical interpretation and implementation of the sFlt-1 / PlGF ratio in the prediction, diagnosis and management of preeclampsia. *Pregnancy Hypertens An Int J Women’s Cardiovasc Heal* [Internet]. 2022;27(August 2021):42–50. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.preghy.2021.12.003>
3. Zeisler H, Llorba E, Chantraine F, Vatish M, Staff AC, Sennström M, et al. Predictive Value of the sFlt-1:PlGF Ratio in Women with Suspected Preeclampsia. *N Engl J Med*. 2016;374(1):13–22.
4. Ohkuchi A, Saito S, Yamamoto T, Minakami H, Masuyama H. Short-term prediction of preeclampsia using the sFlt-1 / PlGF ratio : a subanalysis of pregnant Japanese women from the PROGNOSIS Asia study. *Hypertens Res* [Internet]. 2021;44:813–21. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1038/s41440-021-00629-x>

5. Ding G, Liping L, Moli D, Wuliyeti A, Shaoh Z, Chen P, et al. A study of the association between the sFlt-1 / PIGF ratio and preeclampsia in Xinjiang Uygur Autonomous Region of China. *Artif Cells, Nanomedicine, Biotechnol* [Internet]. 2019;46(S3):S281–6. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1080/21691401.2018.1491480>
6. Stepan H, Hund M, Gencay M, Denk B, Dinkel C, Kaminski WE, et al. A comparison of the diagnostic utility of the sFlt-1 / PIGF ratio versus PIGF alone for the detection of preeclampsia / HELLP syndrome. *Hypertens Pregnancy* [Internet]. 2016;35(3):295–305. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.3109/10641955.2016.1141214>
7. Zhu M, Liu J, Cao J, Ni Y, Chang M, Chen R, et al. Validation of a new kit for preeclampsia screening : A comprehensive analysis. *Heliyon* [Internet]. 2024;10(6):e28080. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e28080>
8. Nikuei P, Rajaei M, Roozbeh N, Mohseni F, Poordarvishi F, Azad M. Diagnostic accuracy of sFlt1 / PIGF ratio as a marker for preeclampsia. *BMC Pregnancy Childbirth*. 2020;20(80):4–9.
9. Serudji J, Basyir V, Tara Fadhillah. Differentiating Maternal Angiogenesis Factors between Early and Late Onset Preeclampsia: Higher sflt-1 in Early Onset Preeclampsia, Lower PIGF and Higher sflt-1/PIGF Ratio in Late Onset Preeclampsia. *Mol Cell Biomed Sci*. 2024;8(3):154–8.